

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Acronyms and abbreviations

LFT	Long-fibre thermoplastic
NF	Natural fibre
PP	Polypropylene polymer
GF	Glass fibre
CF	Carbon fibre
rCF	Recycled carbon fibre
CRF	Centro Ricerche Fiat
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
MFR	Melt flow rate
ABS	Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene polymer
PLA	Polylactic acid polymer
UV	Ultra-violet
NIR	Near infrared spectroscopy
SEM	Scanning electron microscope
TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
HDT	Heat deflection temperature
PC	Polycarbonate
LNF	Long natural fibre
EoL	End of Life
FRP	Fibre reinforced plastic
PE	Polyethylene
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride polymer
WPC	Wood plastic composite
GFRP	Glass fibre reinforced plastic
EU	European Union
TRL	Technology readiness level
HDPE	High density polyethylene
MOR	Modulus of rupture
MOE	Modulus of elasticity
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
WTB	Wind turbine blade
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
IR	Infra-red

1 Introduction

This report will collect all the relevant aspects related to the manufacture and re-manufacture of Automotive components after N-cycles of the composite-based products in the three industrial lines, namely; pultrusion, compounding and agglomeration technologies. The definitions of recycling versus re-manufacturing will be discussed in relation to EcoBulk, covering the period M18 (Nov 2018) till M36 (May 2020). This WP runs M12 to M45 and therefore not all the tasks are complete.

Please note this report is Public and therefore some of the important data is not fully detailed.

In the following chapters we describe how the materials developed in WP3 have been manufactured into components and then reclaimed and re-manufactured by the project partners. Key material data and test results will be presented for the virgin materials and for subsequent re-uses of the materials through re-manufacturing routes.

In the first part of WP4, the partners Conenor, Tecnar, Coventive Composites (NetComposites), Maier and Moretti have optimized agglomeration and compounding technologies and optimized materials formulations to realize new products for the target applications. Several prototype samples have been developed. Prototype samples for building applications realized by Conenor have effectively incorporated high fractions of recovered materials.

All the prototypes have been characterized by morphological and mechanical tests. The thermal stability and the water absorption behaviour of the composites was also investigated (CNR). Specific tests have been performed to demonstrate the recyclability and the re-manufacturability of the realized materials and products at the end of their life.

The resulting data is passed forward to WP6 where it informs the circular manufacturing business model and to WP7 where it informs the LCA of automotive products. It also informs WP8 in relation to business models and exploitation.

The work in this period was planned as below. Some of the work has been completed to this timescale but some has been delayed where COVID-19 has affected, for example, the availability of people to do the work or the access to workshops or equipment. This is noted in the text.

Responsible	Task	2019											
		J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	
COVENTIVE, TECNARO	Production & Supply of ECOBULK compounds to MAIER - quantities to be defined to accommodate production of old and new Fascia panels	█											
MAIER	Mould old version of Fascia with commercial materials (ABS, PC, PP-GF, PP-Talc) and ECOBULK compounds (PP-NF, PP-LNF, PLA) - quantities to be defined	█											
CRF	Mould dashboard component from Jeep Renegade using ECOBULK materials - quantity to be defined	█											
BELLVER	Shredding and grinding of old Fascia panels + CRF components			█									
AIMPLAS	Compounding & homogenisation of 3 families of grinded materials (ABS & PC, PP, PLA) - production of ABS & PC - R1, PP-R1, PLA-R1 compounds					█							
MAIER	Preliminary tests on new Fascia tool. Small quantities of material to ensure that good preparation is done before moulding large quantities of recycled and virgin ECOBULK materials				█								
MAIER	Mould new version of Fascia with combination of virgin and recycled compounds: front side - virgin compounds; back side - recycled compounds							█					
MAIER	Component testing: dimensional control, stiffness under load, heat ageing, impact test, assembly test, dismantling test									█			

2 Circular economy considerations

As a relatively new concept, the definition of “re-manufacturing” varies across industrial sectors and organisations. For the purposes of the EcoBulk project, at least in the automotive sector, the aim, broadly, is to manufacture goods that are fit for purpose, and which that, at EoL, can be reclaimed and re-used to make something similar in design and specification by recycling the raw materials.

Clearly there are several contributory factors to this being possible; the design, the legislation, the reclamation systems and these are covered elsewhere in EcoBulk. In this report we are concentrating on the materials and whether they can survive multiple cycles of use and re-manufacturing.

Figure 1 Scheme of an ideal circular economy

For this WP the raw material suppliers are Coventive (PP-LNF), Tecnar (biopolyester based compounds ECO2.X; polyolefin based compounds ECO1.X) and Maier (ABS/ABS-PC/ABS-GF etc.). Supplied materials were processed into automotive parts at Maier, CRF and Microcab. Demonstrators are then dismantled and sorted at automotive part producers/manufacturers and shipped to Bellver and Aimplas for shredding, cleaning, grinding and compounding of recycled materials into new recycled formulations

Figure 2 Material Production activity.

MicroCab have produced some nice visual representations of how Lifetime Cycles can be fully optimised.

Figure 3 Optimised Lifecycles envisioned by MicroCab

ECOBULK materials developed by Coventive (PP-LNF) and Tecnaro (biopolyester based and polyolefine based compounds) were supplied to Maier, CRF and Microcab to perform 1st loop production trials. In addition to these materials, commercially available grades will be used as well (i.e. ABS and PP based compounds). A total of three material families were used (PP, biopolyester and ABS based compounds).

In addition to the automotive circular model there has also been work to re-manufacture waste materials from a wider source. Conenor are taking multiple waste streams, grinding them to usable granules and re-manufacturing using extrusion processes to manufacture construction and street furniture products.

For the thermoplastic composites being used in EcoBulk they key issues are

- Can the end-of-life components be broken back down to their constituent parts
- When separated, can the materials be reground to a suitable format for re-using
- Can the materials be re-manufactured using standard technology (the same as the original production ideally)
- Once remanufactured, do the materials retain their properties
 - Polymers degrade in multiple heating cycles
 - Reinforcements get shorter, distorted and less effective
- Do additional virgin materials have to be added
- How many times can this be done before degradation precludes re-use.

These are the questions we address in the following sections.

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3 Sample Mouldings for Re-manufacture Tests

Three families of materials have been used: PP, biopolyester and ABS based compounds. These families of materials will be injection moulded into the following parts:

- Maier – injection moulded version 2009 Fascia console
- CRF – injection moulded 4WD control frame
- Microcab – compression moulded dashboard component

The parts are shown below.

Figure 4 Parts used in the Re-manufacture tests

Figure 5 Validation Test Flow Diagram

After the automotive parts were manufactured, they were dismantled, sorted and sent to Bellver for shredding, grinding and cleaning. At this point, recycled granules of three material families (i.e. ABS, PP and biopolyester based) were obtained, which were then sent to AIMPLAS and Tecnaro for mixing, compounding and homogenisation.

It should be noted here that AIMPLAS have experienced, as of May 2020, a delay of at least 2 months as the pilot plant had reduced hours because of COVID issues and the effort put into the development of reusable plastic face masks is support of health services. They hope to resume more normal operations in June 2020.

3.1 Conenor

3.1.1 Materials Used

Conenor developments in Ecobulk relate to utilisation of polymeric waste materials in combination with reinforcing organic (natural) and inorganic (glass) fibres in the matrix. The main invention is a new developed patented technique called “agglomeration” to produce new raw material formulations from waste and recycled materials. Various different material formulations using recycled and virgin thermoplastics PE and PP together with GFRP-based End of Life wind turbine blade waste and GFRP-product manufacturing waste and wood fibres plus additives have been developed and used in the development and manufacturing Ecobulk components for the demonstrations presented in the D4.4 plan.

The list of materials used is the following;

- GFRP-waste from shredding EoL wind turbine blades, suppliers Virol and Demacq, Holland (material formulations in the multilayer product core layer)
- GFRP-waste in shavings from product manufacturing, supplier Exel Composites, Finland (material formulations in the multilayer product surface layer)
- wood fibres in 8mm dia size compressed pellets, manufacturer Versowood, Finland
- recycled HDPE and PP plastics in washed flakes, mixed colours from post-consumer products i.e. bottles and canisters, supplier Swerec, Sweden
- wasted plastic pipes multilayer HDPE and mineral filled PP, supplier PHJ, Finland
- virgin HDPE and PP plastics in granules and fine grain, various qualities from international suppliers
- talc (mineral powder), manufacturer Mondo Minerals, Finland
- additives i.e. processing aid, coupling agent (g-MAH), compatibilizer, color pigments, UV-stabilizer from international suppliers

Well over 100 different formulations were tested and therefore not listed here in detail, but the following principles were used;

- **multilayer product surface layer formulation** is using GFRP-waste from manufacturing 35%-w. and a mix of recycled and virgin plastics some 35%-w. (either HDPE or PP) and wood fibres some 15%-w. and 10%-w. talc plus the rest of all listed additives
- **multilayer product core layer formulation** is using GFRP-waste from EoL wind turbine blades 35%-w. and recycled plastics some 25%-w. (either HDPE or PP) and wood fibres some 25%-w. and 10%-w. talc plus from the additives processing aid, coupling agent and compatibilizer but not colour pigments nor UV-stabilizer

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Note that different recycled plastic qualities are all not the same but different and also there are variations in Swerec batches in each of the 1 tonne bags supplied. Obviously this is causing some variations in processing stability as well as in manufactured product quality.

Figure 6 Photos of EoL wind turbine blades supplied in shredded form in big bags

Figure 7 Photos of wasted filled PP-pipes at PHJ and those downsized at Conenor

Figure 8 Photos of recycled plastic flakes, wasted multilayer HDPE-pipes, additives in granule form, wood fibre pellets and virgin plastic granules

The prototype profiles realized by CONENOR as detailed in the Deliverable 3.1 and above were selected to perform re-manufacturing processes. Different re-manufactured prototypes were realized and tested to evaluate difference in the overall performances of the re-manufactured prototypes with respect to the original ones.

In particular, the following prototypes samples were selected, re-manufactured at CONENOR industrial plant, and tested at CNR facilities.

- S37 1 re-manufacturing process
- S39 1 re-manufacturing process
- S40 1 re-manufacturing process
- S43 2 consecutive re-manufacturing processes
- S44 2 consecutive re-manufacturing processes

3.1.2 Processes Used

Conenor is using three different processes and equipment in manufacturing circular composite materials and products and re-manufacturing the material back to original products. They are;

- Agglomeration process for manufacturing recycled circular raw materials
- Re-grinding process for downsizing composite materials and products
- Multilayer extrusion with 2-rotor CONEX[®]

These processes are described shortly below and used in this sequential order.

Agglomeration process for manufacturing recycled circular raw materials

Note: the same process from step 2 is used also for drying composite materials after re-grinding to remove residual moisture (if found necessary) for re-manufacturing

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Figure 9 Conenor Process

The Conenor invented agglomeration process for waste, recycled and re-manufactured materials is described in details in deliverable D3.1; Development of the intermediate materials for composite production.

Re-grinding process for downsizing composite materials and products

Re-grinding composite products is made using a rotary 3-blade grinder type Rapid 300 having a 7,5kW motor. Existing sieve sizes currently are 6/10/16mm and typically 10mm has been used to produce proper particle size material. Depending on product shape and size in question and how sharp blades are at the moment, the equipment can deliver +/- 1ton per hour re-grinded material.

Figure 10 Re-grinding Conenor manufactured GFRP-composite planks with Rapid 300

Figure 11 Re-grinded composite material ready for re-manufacturing (or intermediate drying)

Multilayer extrusion with 2-rotor CONEX®

Multilayer 2-rotor extruder CONEX® is a patented invention of Conenor since the 1990s'. However, it is not the only extrusion process existing to produce multilayer product structures but conventional co-extrusion process is commonly used worldwide in the plastic processing market.

A Schematic diagram of 2-rotor CONEX®-extruder principle for manufacturing various multilayer product structures is presented in figure 12 below. The same principle and equipment is used for both hollow and solid products and in alternative product shapes i.e. planks, panels, pillars, beams etc. and sizes just by changing the die parts in question adequate for each product. In case single material/layer product is produced, just one material formulation becomes in use.

The multilayer extruder concept is based in multiple conical rotors nested inside each other and separated with heated stators. Individual material formulations are fed to each rear and front rotors by two feeding screws placed at 3 and 9 o'clock positions for uniform filling of the root of the rotor. Multilayer tubular shaped 2-material flow is formed right after the front rotor tip on mandrel fixed to rear stator and surrounded on outer surface by an adapter followed by die parts for forming the product shape in question fixed to the face of the extruder front stator.

The material formulation being fed into the rear rotor (mix #1) is used for re-manufacturing the material derived from the composite product re-grinding process.

Figure 12 Schematic diagram of 2-rotor CONEX®-extruder for multilayer products

3.1.3 Case Study Photos and Descriptions

Case studies as Ecobulk multilayer pilot product types produced at Conenor having re-manufactured composite material in the product core layer are displayed below in figures 13 and 14

They all follow the same principle and pattern as described in previous sections. Surface layer of the products is always made separately from non-re-manufactured materials and each product is utilizing re-manufactured material in the embedded product core hollow or solid. There are over 100 compositions of the the re-manufactured materials described in the in deliverable D3.1; Development of the intermediate materials for composite production.

All Ecobulk materials and formulations developed and processed by Conenor have become 99% re-manufactured into the demo products and test samples. It is worth noting HDPE-based formulations are not mixed together with PP-based formulations, they are kept separate.

The quantity of re-manufactured material in the core layer formulation can vary/be used anything between 0 to 100%-w. depending on product shape and dimensions and quality criteria in question – as well as how much re-manufactured material happens to be available time to time for production. As revealed in tentative test results, re-manufactured Ecobulk composite material developed by Conenor is qualitatively quite okay to be used even up to 100% alone and in several loops in the same products in construction and outdoor furniture applications.

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The relative proportion of the core layer containing re-manufactured material vs. surface layer in weight is different depending on extruded product shape and layer thickness. In the solid 30mm thick plank (left up) the core layer represents some $\frac{3}{4}$ of total product weight, in hollow 28mm thick plank and hollow pillar with 10mm wall (right up and left down) $\frac{1}{2}$ and 10mm thick solid panel (right down) some $\frac{1}{3}$.

Figure 13 Multilayer composite pilot products with core layer utilizing re-manufactured material

PCT-patent application on multilayer product structures with GFRP-waste

January 2020 Conenor filed an international pct-patent application for multilayer product structures with at least one layer consisting of material utilizing GFRP-waste. Some alternative structures displayed below in figure 14.

The core layer in such products is optimally used also for re-manufactured materials.

an

Figure 14 Alternative multilayer product structures in Conenor pct-patent application

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CNR analysed the samples prepared by Conenor. The original samples were hollow profiles with an approximate length of about 120 cm, whose images are reported in Figure 15 Image of original profiles coded as S37, S39, S40, S43, S44. The lateral image of the profile S37 is also shown on the right.

Figure 15 Image of original profiles coded as S37, S39, S40, S43, S44. The lateral image of the profile S37 is also shown on the right, as an example

Table 1 Composition of the prototype samples produced by CONENOR.

Sample	Amounts (wt%)					
	Matrix	Fillers	Processing aid	Maleated coupling agent	Pigment	Other additives
S37	Bio HDPE (virgin) 30	Wood* 62	4	2	2	-
S39	Recycled HDPE 40	Wood** + GFRP from WTB*** 25 + 25	4	2	2	2

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S40	Recycled HDPE 40	Wood** + GFRP from WTB*** 20 + 30	4	2	2	2
S43	Virgin PP 40	Wood** + GFRP from WTB*** 20 + 30	4	2	2	2
S44	Recycled HDPE (UPO)**** 31.5	Wood** + GFRP from WTB*** 30 + 30	4	2.5	-	2

* from furniture waste

** from construction and demolition waste

*** glass-fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP) from dismantled wind turbine blades (WTB)

**** from dismantled multilayer pipes

3.2 Maier

Maier worked on a fascia moulding for this EcoBulk task.

Description of the Component

The ECOBULK Fascia developed by MAIER as functional prototype is a component that includes different parts made of injected plastic, joined to the cockpit with standard snap fits moulded on back of the parts. The electric+electronic devices (audio, video, GPS, etc.) are fixed with a metallic frame to the fascia and cockpit by standard fasteners (steel screws and nuts). The design of the ECOBULK Fascia is based on commercial versions of similar applications currently produced by MAIER. This prototype fascia has been re-designed to be injected by a 2K moulding process. The front side of the part is made of a conventional plastic material to obtain the high-quality aesthetic functionality. The back side includes the same structural functionalities than the commercial version. A number of ECOBULK materials (bioplastics, recycled) has been injected on this back side to evaluate the performance of the ECOBULK Fascia compared to the commercial versions. As those ECOBULK materials are fully compatible to the plastic injected on the front side of the part, there is no need to dismantle and recycle separately the aesthetic and structural elements of the application.

Figure 16 Fascia 2009 showing the Central Console

3.2.1 Materials Used

The plastic materials for the production of sample parts by MAIER were selected according to the results of WP3. All the formulations are thermoplastic compounds, based on three different kind of polymers: styrenics (ABS, PC+ABS); polyolefins (PP Homopolymer, PP Copolymer); and Bioplastics. Most of these polymers are modified with mineral fillers (MF) and/or fibres (Carbon (CF), Glass (GF), and (long) Natural Fibre(s) ((L)NF)).

Code	Type	Supplier
PLA00005	ABS	MAIER
PLA00011	ABS-GF8	MAIER
ECO2.8	PLA-MF	TECNARO
ECO3.7	PLA-GF	TECNARO
PLA00137	PP-GF30	MAIER
PLA00129	PP-T20	MAIER
ECO1.4	PP-NF	TECNARO

Thermoplastic compounds, based on two different types of polymers: polyolefins (ECO1.X family) and biopolyesters (ECO2.X family), modified with different natural fibres (long and short), mineral fillers and stabilising additives, were selected for re-manufacture tests according to the results obtained in WP3. The mechanical, thermo-mechanical and rheological properties of selected ECOBULK materials are summarized in the following tables. ECO1.5 shows the best mechanical performance of ECO1.X-family and ECO2.8 shows best thermal stability of ECO2.X-family. Materials ECO2.7-ECO3.7 are optimized in terms of hydrolysis and UV-stabilization to prevent polymer degradation and to improve the durability and recyclability.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of selected ECO1.X materials:

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Compound	Tensile (E)-modulus [MPa]	Tensile Stress at break [MPa]	Tensile Strain at break [%]	Max. Tensile Stress [MPa]	Max. Tensile Strain [%]	Charpy Impact strength (23 °C) [kJ/m ²]	Shrinkage [%]
ECO1.1	2750	27	3	28	3	14	
ECO1.3	1900	25	3	25	3	11	0,61%
ECO1.5	3030	57	6	57	6	48	1,00%

Table 3 Thermo-mechanical and rheological properties of selected ECO1.X materials:

Compound	MVR 190°C/ 2,16kg [cm ³ /10 min]	HDT-B [°C]	moisture content
ECO1.1	5	101	0,05
ECO1.3	6	100	0
ECO1.5	3	142	0,04

Table 4 Mechanical properties of selected ECO2.X and ECO3.X materials:

Compound	Tensile (E)-modulus [MPa]	Tensile Stress at break [MPa]	Tensile Strain at break [%]	Max. Tensile Stress [MPa]	Max. Tensile Strain [%]	Charpy Impact strength (23 °C) [kJ/m ²]	Shrinkage [%]
ECO2.1	3450	16	12	43	2	P230	0,67%
ECO2.2	3150	20	24	47	3	P240	0,80%
ECO2.7	3060	22	28	45	3	P157	0,75%
ECO2.8	3800	23	9	52	2	56	0,54%
ECO2.9	2420	46	3	54	3	P150	0,48%
ECO3.0	3620	10	5	50	2	90	0,40%
ECO3.7	8360	104	2	105	2	27	0,64%
B4S	6180	81	2	81	2	21	0,33%

Table 5 Thermo-mechanical and rheological properties of selected ECO2.X and ECO3.X materials:

Compound	MVR 190°C/ 2,16kg [ml/10 min]	VICAT A [°C]	HDT-B [°C]	moisture content
ECO2.1	7	110		0,05
ECO2.2	4	110		0,06
ECO2.7	2	111	53	0,05
ECO2.8	2	114	54	0,09
ECO2.9	7	62	53	0,07
ECO3.0	4	64	53	0,07
ECO3.7	1	81	57	0,05
B4S	6	71	55	0,09

ECO1.1, ECO1.3 and ECO1.5. and materials based on polyolefins modified with MF and/or fibres (CF, GF, and/or NF) were also developed by Maier and injected into Fascia 2009 parts at Maier`s facilities. The Fascia 2009 parts were shipped for shredding to Bellver. Bellver shipped the shredded material to AIMPLAS. AIMPLAS is going to mix and extrude all materials based on polyolefins to form *ECOPP-R1* granules.

ECO2.1, ECO2.2, ECO2.7, ECO2.9 and ECO3.0 based on biopolyesters were provided to MAIER. Injected sample parts (Fascia 2009) were send by Maier to Bellver (ca. 100 Kg each). Bellver shipped the shredded material to AIMPLAS. AIMPLAS is going to mix and extrude all materials based on biopolyesters to form *ECOPLA-R1* granules.

The same procedure was performed on ABS materials and compounds to produce *ECOABS-R1* by AIMPLAS.

Table 6 Used materials for recycling to form: ECOABS-R1, ECOPLA-R1 and ECOPP-R1:

Code	Type	(kg)
PLA00005	ABS	52,8
PLA00011	ABS-GF8	24,0
PLA00079	PC+ABS	24,0
ECOABS-R1	ABS	100,8
ECO2.1	PLA- MF	11,5
ECO2.2	PLA- MF	11,6
ECO2.7	PLA- MF	18,0
ECO2.9	PLA	16,7
ECO3.0	PLA- MF	17,5
B4S	PLA-GF	25,1
ECOPLA-R1	PLA	100,29
PLA00128	PP-T20	18,7

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PLA00137	PP-GF30	25,4
ECO1.1	PP-NF	9,1
ECO1.3	PP-NF	13,6
ECO1.5	PP-LNF	13,6
MTC089	PP-NF30	17,9
Jute/GF 1.1	PP-(NF+GF)40	9,5
ECOPP-R1	PP	107,73

For the processing of **ECOPLA-R2** (50 kg/ 50% recycled): 25 Kg of **ECOPLA-R1** (50%) and 25 kg virgin ECO2.8 biopolyester-compound (favourite compound) will be compounded at AIMPLAS.

For the processing of **ECOPP-R2** (50 kg/ 50% recycled): Maier will provide a PP-T20 compound and for **ECOABS-R2** virgin ABS to AIMPLAS.

Table 7 Used materials for the processing of: ECOABS-R2, ECOPLA-R2 and ECOPP-R2:

Supplier	Type	(kg)	(%)
MAIER	ABS	25	50,0
ECOBULK	ABS-R1	25	50,0
ECOABS-R2	ABS-R2	50	100,0
MAIER	PP-T20	25	50,0
ECOBULK	PP-R1	25	50,0
ECOPP-R2	PP-R2	50	100,0
TECNARO	PLA-MF	25	50,0
ECOBULK	PLA-R1	25	50,0
ECOPLA-R2	PLA-R2	50	100,0

3.2.2 Processes Used

The prototype injection mould for the production of Fascia ECOBULK sample parts has been designed and built by MAIER specifically for the 2K injection with a non-conventional injection

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machine Engel 700. Both the mould and the injection machine had been set-up for the production of parts under fully automated conditions, according to the industrial standards of productivity and quality. The peripheral equipment of the injection machine includes pre-drying system, automated pneumatic feeding system, mould heaters, and a robotic system for the demoulding and manipulation of the parts. The following pictures show a general view of the prototype mould and the injection machine during the production of ECOBULK samples. Further details of the processing parameters will be included in D4.5 (M45).

Figure 17 ECOBULK Fascia. Prototype Injection mould.

Figure 18 Injection moulding machine at MAIER facilities.

Process used for the Fascia 2009

The prototype sample parts Fascia 2009 (monomaterial version) were produced at MAIER facilities with a conventional standard injection moulding machine KraussMaffei KM500-2700C2. Some peripheral equipment (pre-drying system, pneumatic feeding system, mould heaters) were need to

set-up the production of the parts. The process parameters were optimized according to the results of the preliminary injection trails performed by MAIER on WP3

Figure 19 Fascia 2009. Injection mould (left) and injection moulding machine (right). Production of plastic sample part at MAIER facilities.

3.2.3 Case study for the ECOBULK Fascia

Sample parts

Samples of the ECOBULK Fascia (2K version) produced by MAIER so far are coded to identify properly the different combination of ECOBULK materials used to inject the parts: Material #1 on front side (aesthetic); Material #2 on back side (structural).

Some activities are currently ongoing at MAIER to apply conventional post-processes (aerographic painting) on these samples to improve the aesthetic finish of the front side. Both non-painted and painted sample parts are under evaluation, to check the real performance of the prototype ECOBULK Fascia compared to the conventional mono-material painted parts on the market.

Sample	Material #1 (Front Side)		Material #2 (Back Side)	
	Code	Type	Code	Type
10	PLA00005	ABS	PLA00011	ABS-GF8
11	PLA00005	ABS	ECO2.8	PLA-MF
12	PLA00005	ABS	ECO3.7	PLA-GF
13	PLA00129	PP-T20	PLA00137	PP-GF30
14	PLA00129	PP-T20	ECO1.4	PP-NF

Figure 20 Sample #12: ABS / PLA-GF

Figure 21 Sample #14: P/E-T20 / PP-NF

Test Results

The validation tests on the prototype fascia (2K virgin ECOBULK materials) are currently ongoing at MAIER, including the painting and the assembly/dismantling tests on the parts.

The results of the injection trials and validation test on prototype sample parts made of recycled materials **ECOBULK-R1** (100% recycled) and **ECOBULK-R2** (50% recycled) will be reported in D4.5 (M45).

Demonstrator

The design of the functional prototype ECOBULK Fascia has been done to fulfil the technical specifications regarding the functionality of the automotive interior applications, including the technical requirements for the assembly/dismantling operations of each of the individual parts of the cockpit.

The Automotive Demonstrator ECOBULK Fascia performed by MAIER is currently placed at MAIER Technology Centre facilities, as part of the showrooms available for the periodic workshops and

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technical meetings organized by MAIER in collaboration with European OEMs of the Automotive sector.

Some activities are ongoing to finish the set-up of the Demonstrator to evaluate the performance of the different versions of the ECOBULK Fascia under evaluation (virgin materials, recycled materials). The results of the preliminary trials on ECOBULK fascia (virgin material) show a good performance of the components. Following an “easy-to-do” procedure, the whole assembly/dismantling operations can be completed by hand and using simple tools like standard screwdriver. This method allows both the maintenance operations (substitution of damaged elements, update of electric+electronic devices) and the dismantling at the End of Life of the vehicle. Further details will be reported in D4.5 (M45).

Figure 22 ECOBULK Fascia. Showroom demonstrator at MAIER Technology Centre facilities

Figure 23 ECOBULK Fascia. Video Display Screen Assembly and Air Conditioning Vents Assembly

Figure 24 Fascia+ Air Conditioning Vents+ Dashboard Trims and electronic devices

3.2.4 Case study for the Fascia 2009

ECO1.1, ECO1.3 and ECO1.5. together with materials based on polyolefins modified with MF and/or fibres (CF, GF, and/or NF) developed by Maier were injected into Fascia 2009 parts at Maier's facilities. The Fascia 2009 parts were shipped for shredding to Bellver. Bellver shipped the shredded material to AIMPLAS. AIMPLAS is going to mix and extrude all materials based on polyolefins to form **ECOPP-R1** granules.

ECO2.1, ECO2.2, ECO2.7, ECO2.9, ECO3.0 and B4S based on biopolyesters were provided to MAIER. Injected sample parts (Fascia 2009) were send by Maier to Bellver (ca. 100 Kg each). Bellver shipped the shredded material to AIMPLAS. AIMPLAS is going to mix and extrude all materials based on biopolyesters to form **ECOPLA-R1** granules.

The same procedure was performed on ABS materials and compounds by MAIER to produce **ECOABS-R1** by AIMPLAS.

Table 8 Used materials for recycling to form: **ECOABS-R1, ECOPLA-R1 and ECOPP-R1:**

Code	Type	(kg)
PLA00005	ABS	52,8
PLA00011	ABS-GF8	24,0
PLA00079	PC+ABS	24,0
ECOABS-R1	ABS	100,8
ECO2.1	PLA- MF	11,5
ECO2.2	PLA- MF	11,6
ECO2.7	PLA- MF	18,0
ECO2.9	PLA	16,7
ECO3.0	PLA- MF	17,5
B4S	PLA-GF	25,1

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ECOPLA-R1	PLA	100,29
PLA00128	PP-T20	18,7
PLA00137	PP-GF30	25,4
ECO1.1	PP-NF	9,1
ECO1.3	PP-NF	13,6
ECO1.5	PP-LNF	13,6
MTC089	PP-NF30	17,9
Jute/GF 1.1	PP-(NF+GF)40	9,5
ECOPP-R1	PP	107,73

For the processing of *ECOPLA-R2* (50 kg/ 50% recycled): 25 Kg of **ECOPLA-R1** (50%) and 25 kg virgin ECO2.8 biopolyester compound (favourite compound) will be compounded at AIMPLAS.

For the processing of *ECOPP-R2* (50 kg/ 50% recycled): Maier will provide a PP-T20 compound and for *ECOABS-R2* virgin ABS to AIMPLAS.

Table 9 Used materials for the processing of: ECOABS-R2, ECOPLA-R2 and ECOPP-R2:

Supplier	Type	(kg)	(%)
MAIER	ABS	25	50,0
ECOBULK	ABS-R1	25	50,0
ECOABS-R2	ABS-R2	50	100,0
MAIER	PP-T20	25	50,0
ECOBULK	PP-R1	25	50,0
ECOPP-R2	PP-R2	50	100,0
TECNARO	PLA-MF	25	50,0
ECOBULK	PLA-R1	25	50,0
ECOPLA-R2	PLA-R2	50	100,0

Figure 25 Fascia Parts by Maier

Injection moulded Fascia Version 2009 parts by Maier based on different materials (from left to right): Fascia 2009 part based on ABS (left), Fascia 2009 part based on a biopolyester compound (middle) and a Fascia 2009 part based on a PP-compound. Validation test on a Fascia Version 2009 part (right).

Figure 26 Left side: injection moulding process at Maier. Right side: shredded Fascia 2009 parts (Bellver).

3.3 Microcab

3.3.1 Materials Used

Microcab have worked closely with Coventive to produce prototype parts

The materials used are manufactured by Coventive as Long Fibre Thermoplastic (LFT) pellets.

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Property	Specification	Details
Polymers	Polypropylene MFR: 20 - 150 g/10 min	Other polymers may be used
Fibres	Jute, flax , glass fibre, carbon fibre , recycled carbon fibre	Single use or a combination of these materials is possible
Pellet sizes	Diameter: 4.0 – 4.5 mm Length: 10 – 15 mm	Standard pellet length = 12 mm
Fibre weight and volume fractions	30 – 40 %wt (20 - 30% volume)	Higher fibre volume fractions not recommended due to poor fibre impregnation
Output (minimum)	4.0 kg/hour	Processing parameters have been optimised for this line speed
Typical batch size	3 – 10 kg	3 kg: 1 hour run at min. speed 10 kg: 2 hours run at max. speed

Figure 27 LFT materials used

All of the materials used for this period were NF-based but in latter stages recycled CF pellets were produced in small quantities, which can used in the latter part of the project.

Figure 28 Early rCF production

The initial properties of the samples made are shown in Table 10

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Reference	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Density (g/cm ³)
Jute – PP LFT 1.1	4.9	28.9	0.95
Jute – PP LFT 1.2	4.6	27.7	0.97
Jute – PP LFT 1.3	4.6	37.4	0.93
Jute – PP LFT 1.4	6.5	51.5	1.03
Jute/GF – PP LFT 1.1	5.8	31.8	1.01
Jute/GF – PP LFT 1.2	6.4	60.8	1.06
Jute/CF – PP LFT 1.1	7.3	36.2	0.97
rCF – PP LFT 1.1	12.5	104.2	1.01

Table 10 NF LFT properties

3.3.2 Processes Used

The chosen dashboard samples were manufactured by a simple compression moulding process. This is a low-cost way of manufacturing usable samples for prototype vehicles of the type Microcab are currently developing. It also allows comparative testing of re-manufactured parts.

The tool was designed and manufactured by Microcab, the mouldings were made at the Coventive facility

Figure 29 Compression moulding tool and parts

3.3.3 Case Study Photos and Descriptions

The resultant mouldings were trimmed and demonstrated as working prototypes

Figure 30 Microcab prototype mouldings

3.4 Tecnar

3.4.1 Materials Used

Compounds realized at TECNARO were delivered to CNR for re-manufacturing tests.

In particular, the following compounds were selected by TECNARO, re-manufactured and tested at CNR facilities. 2 re-manufacturing cycles were performed for each of the selected compounds.

ECO 1.1

ECO 1.9

ECO 1.10

3.4.2 Processes Used

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The processes used to realize the compounds ECO_1.1, ECO_1.9 and ECO_1.10 are detailed in the Deliverable D3.1.

3.4.3 Descriptions

Details on the composition of the above mentioned compounds are briefly summarized in the Deliverable D3.1.

4 Re-Manufacturing Methodologies and Loops Carried out

In this section the partners describe the work down to manufacture, remanufacture and loop the materials through a re-use process.

4.1 Conenor

Initially in the recycled composite material formulations' development phase in WP3 Conenor produced a few material samples with re-manufacturing loops described hereafter;

- 1) first manufacturing the original material formulation in the agglomeration process
- 2) manufacturing single layer extruded hollow profiles in size 60x40x8mm using the agglomerates
- 3) re-grinding the extruded profiles into re-manufacturable particle size using 10mm sieve in the Rapid 300 re-grinder
- 4) re-manufacturing in extrusion in the same equipment again the same profile using the re-grinded material – and adding just +2% processing aid in the material
- 5) the product coming out from 4) going back in 3) for the next loop

Understanding that the main raw materials used in the original material formulation in the agglomeration process were sourced as recycled materials, the first manufacturing is considered as 1st re-manufacturing loop, and the loop following the first considered as 2nd and one more thereafter the 3rd loop.

Processing showed no problems in any steps, it was easy way straight forward “just do it”.

Equal samples 1m long from each loop were supplied to CNR testing and results are presented in D3.1 and summarized in a chart in section 5.4.

At CNR, in order to produce the re-manufactured samples, coded as S37-2, S39-2, S40-2 (for these profiles only 1 re-manufacturing cycle was performed) and S43-2, S43-3, S44-2 and S44-3 (for these profiles 2 re-manufacturing cycles were performed), original profiles were crushed and grinded until an average granulometry of about 0.5 cm was obtained.

Therefore, the obtained granules were re-processed using the original processing cycle, already described in D3.1. No further additives or additional thermoplastic PP or HDPE phase were added during the re-manufacturing

4.2 Maier

Details on the methodology proposed by MAIER for the design of the component, selection of materials, assembly/dismantling operations, and recycling of automotive plastic parts are further described in D5.2

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The following is a description of the activities performed by MAIER so far to evaluate the recycling/re-manufacture of the prototype sample parts, with the target of producing new prototype Fascia ECOBULK made of recycled materials.

Figure 31 Fascia ECOBULK. Recycling/Re-Manufacture of sample parts

According to this procedure, all the sample parts Fascia 2009 injected by MAIER on ECOBULK materials (100% virgin) were sent BELLVER on M28.

After the shredding process by BELLVER for the size reduction of the parts, the samples were sent to AIMPLAS on M30 for the extrusion-compounding of the ECOBULK-R1 materials (100% recycled content) (due date M33 - delayed).

The extrusion of the ECOBULK-R2 materials (50% recycled content) depends on the results of the ECOBULK-R1. A further coordination is needed for the shipment of samples from/to MAIER/TECNARO/COVENTIVE to/from AIMPLAS.

The subsequent injection of new sample parts by MAIER made of recycled materials has been delayed because of COVID issues, (new date to be defined).

Figure 32 Shipment of injected sample parts (left) and after shredding process (right).

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Table 11 Total amount of sample parts (virgin ECOBULK materials) and ECOBULK-R1 materials (100% recycled)

Code	Type	(kg)
PLA00005	ABS	52,8
PLA00011	ABS-GF8	24,0
PLA00079	PC+ABS	24,0
ECOABS-R1	ABS	100,8
ECO2.1	PLA-MF	11,5
ECO2.2	PLA-MF	11,6
ECO2.7	PLA-MF	18,0
ECO2.9	PLA	16,7
ECO3.0	PLA-MF	17,5
B4S	PLA-GF	25,1
ECOPLA-R1	PLA	100,29
PLA00128	PP-T20	18,7
PLA00137	PP-GF30	25,4
ECO1.1	PP-NF	9,1
ECO1.3	PP-NF	13,6
ECO1.5	PP-LNF	13,6
MTC089	PP-NF30	17,9
Jute/GF 1.1	PP-(NF+GF)40	9,5
ECOPP-R1	PP	107,73

Table 12 Total amount of ECOBULK-R2 materials (50% recycled) to be produced.

Supplier	Type	(kg)	(%)
MAIER	ABS	25	50,0
ECOBULK	ABS-R1	25	50,0
ECOABS-R2	ABS-R2	50	100,0

MAIER	PP-T20	25	50,0
ECOBULK	PP-R1	25	50,0
ECO-PP-R2	PP-R2	50	100,0
TECNARO	PLA-MF	25	50,0
ECOBULK	PLA-R1	25	50,0
ECO-PLA-R2	PLA-R2	50	100,0

4.3 Tecnaró

In order to produce re-manufactured samples, the compounds ECO_1.1, ECO_1.9 and ECO_1.10 were compression moulded at CNR using a hot platen press (Dr. Collin P400) equipped with quick cooling cassette. The following heating/cooling cycle were applied. First, the material was allowed to soften in an open mould at 190°C for 10 min at zero pressure, and then pressure was raised to 100 bar and kept for 5 min. Finally, the material was cooled through the cooling cassette system to room temperature by cold water before pressure release. Panels with size of about 10 x 10 x 0.35 cm were obtained.

Re-manufacturing tests were performed by crushing the above detailed samples in a Retch cutting mill equipment. The recovered granules were reprocessed in a twin blade batch mixer (Plastograph EC of Brabender) at 180 °C (set temperature) for 10 min and increasing progressively the mixing speed from 16 to 64 rpm. The compound was then cooled to room temperature, pelletized, and then compression moulded as already described for the virgin compound.

4.4 Coventive

Mouldings were then ground down using a simple commercial grinder and re-manufactured using the compression moulding process.

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Figure 33 Re-manufacturing process loop

5 Test Results

5.1 Maier

Injection moulding process

All the ECOBULK materials injected by MAIER seem to be compatible with injection process with the standard equipment conventionally used to produce automotive components at industrial scale.

Nevertheless, some problems were detected during the injection trials of the compounds reinforced with long fibers. Due to a combination of low density of the material, and large size of the pellets, the standard pneumatic feeding systems of the pre-drying and hopper do not work properly. A non-conventional vibrating system should be implemented to poke the pellets into the hopper.

On the other hand, the same compounds reinforced with natural fiber trend clearly to generate a residual deposit on the surface of the cavity and the splitline of the mould. After a few injection shots, the surface of the mould should be cleaned. Although this maintenance operation can be done by using conventional chemical agents (alcohol), a further investigation should be done to evaluate the effect of this soil on the steel of the mould (rusting, modification of the roughness on the cavity surface).

Figure 34 Pre-drying equipment (left) and feeding system (right). The NF pellets caused problems.

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Figure 35 Fixed Half (Cavity) before (left) and after (right) injection of PP-LNF Materials

Validation tests

The preliminary results of the validation test performed by MAIER on the sample parts made of ECOBULK virgin materials are show below. The same validation tests on the 2K version of the prototype fascia are currently ongoing at MAIER, including the painting of parts, and the assembly/dismantling tests.

The injection trials and validation test on prototype sample parts made of recycled materials ECOBULK-R1 (100% recycled) and ECOBULK-R2 (50% recycled) should be done no later than M40, so these results will we reported on D4.5 (M51) (revised from M45 as the project has been extended)

			ECO1.1	ECO1.3	ECO1.5	Jute/GF 1.1
			PP-NF	PP-NF	PP-LNF	PP-(NF+GF)40
Test description	Method	Specification				
Heat ageing (22h/100°C)	D45 1234	No Change	OK	OK	OK	OK
Light resistance (WOM)	D47 1431					
240 h		Grey Scale index ≥4				
300 h		Grey Scale index ≥3/4				
		No tearing of the film				
Colour fastness to rubbing (10 Cycles)	D45 1010	Degradation =5				

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Dry			OK	OK	OK	OK
Soapy water			OK	OK	OK	OK
Technical Heptane			OK	OK	OK	OK
Essence F			OK	OK	OK	OK
Distilled water			OK	OK	OK	OK
Resistance to micro-organism in humid atmosphere (168h/40°C/95%HR)	D47 1217	No Change	Not Good	Not Good	Not Good	Not Good
Accelerated ageing (168h/40°C/95%HR)	D47 1165	No Change				
	B15 5050		OK	OK	OK	Not Good
Colour fastness to water, sea water and perspiration	D47 1020	Degradation =5 Degorgement =5				
Acid perspiration			OK	OK	OK	OK
Basic perspiration			OK	OK	OK	OK
Chemical resistance (hand cream)	B62 0400	No Change / 10N				
Nivea			OK	Not Good	OK	OK
La Roche-Posay			OK	Not Good	OK	OK

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			ECO2.1	ECO2.2	ECO2.7	ECO2.9	ECO3.0
			PLA-MF	PLA-MF	PLA-MF	PLA	PLA-MF
Test description	Method	Specification					
Heat ageing (22h/100°C)	D45 1234	No Change	OK	OK	OK	Not Good	Not Good
Light resistance (WOM)	D47 1431						
240 h		Grey Scale index ≥ 4	OK	Not Good			
300 h		Grey Scale index $\geq 3/4$	OK	Not Good			
		No tearing of the film	Not Good	Not Good			
Colour fastness to rubbing (10 Cycles)	D45 1010	Degradation =5 Degorgement ≥ 4					
Dry			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Soapy water			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Technical Heptane			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Essence F			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Distilled water			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Resistance to micro-organism in humid atmosphere (168h/40°C/95%HR)	D47 1217	No Change	OK	OK	OK	OK	Not Good
Accelerated ageing (168h/40°C/95%HR)	D47 1165	No Change					
	B15 5050		OK	OK	OK	OK	Not Good
Colour fastness to water, sea water and perspiration	D47 1020	Degradation =5					
Acid perspiration			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Basic perspiration			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Chemical resistance (hand cream)	B62 0400	No Change / 10N					
Nivea			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK

La Roche-Posay			OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
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5.2 Coventive

Parts were tested and the results are shown below. Interestingly there is little degradation, in fact the properties stay quite constant. This is likely to be because the compression moulding process is quite low-stress on the materials. Also, as noted by other partners, the original starting material may not have been as well wetted-out as it could have been and therefore in subsequent cycles the degradation of the polymer and/or fibres is compensated for by the improved fibre-matrix interface. There is also the school of thought that suggests natural fibres are less brittle than glass or carbon fibre and therefore do not suffer the same reduction in size through the re-grind process and retain their properties better.

Figure 36 Mechanical results following recycling loops

The results are not presented as a percentage degradation as there is no significant degradation, any variance is within expected tolerance bands.

5.3 Conenor

All the samples were characterized at CNR through the following tests:

- Density (ASTM D792-13A)
- Flexural tests: Flexural modulus and flexural strength were calculated using the procedures described in ISO 178:2010;

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- Impact tests: The resilience of the composite samples were determined using the procedure described in ISO179-2:1997;

- Water adsorption tests: these tests were performed using an internal CNR procedure. Small specimens (size > 2 cm x 2 cm x original thickness) were obtained by cutting the original profile samples. The specimens were conditioned at 25 °C and 50% relative humidity (RH) for at least 7 days. The weight of each specimen was measured with an analytical balance (± 0.0001 g). The dimension of the specimens were measured with a digital micrometer. The specimens were therefore immersed in distilled water and kept at 25 °C in the dark for 28 days. Therefore, the specimens were removed from water, the excess of water on their surface was gently removed with a filter paper and the specimens were weighted and measured again. The water absorption after 28 days of immersion was calculated (wt%), as well as the max thickness swelling (%) and the max lateral elongation (%). For each sample, at least 5 specimens were tested. Average values and standard deviation values were calculated.

- Thermal stability: the thermal stability of the samples was evaluated by means of a thermogravimetric analyser Perkin Elmer Pyris Diamond TG/DTA. For each sample, small specimens (5 mg < weight < 15 mg) were obtained and analysed under a non-oxidizing flow (gaseous nitrogen). The temperature corresponding to a weight loss of 2 wt% (T 2wt% WL), and to a weight loss of 5 wt% (T 5 wt% WL) was recorded. The weight residual at 800 °C was also measured. For each sample, at least 3 specimens were measured. Average values and standard deviation values were obtained.

Test results on prototype samples S37, S39, S40, S43 and S44 are reported in the tables below. For each re-manufactured prototype sample, differences with respect to the original ones are also reported.

Table 13 Test results of the re-manufactured prototype sample S37-2 with respect to the original prototype S37.

Property/Sample	S37	S37-2	Difference
Density (g/cm³)	1.127 ± 0.010	1.154 ± 0.011	+ 0.027
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	16.8 ± 0.8	9.1 ± 1.4	- 7.7
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	5.4 ± 0.4	2.4 ± 0.3	- 3.0
Max lat elong, 28d (%)	5.9 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.2	- 2.7
Flexural modulus (MPa)	3065 ± 105	4450 ± 85	+ 1385
Flexural strength (MPa)	24.0 ± 0.1	27.9 ± 0.3	+ 3.9

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Resilience (kJ/m²)	3.76 ± 0.18	2.95 ± 0.25	- 0.81
T(2wt% WL) °C	251 ± 2	245 ± 1	- 6
T(5 wt% WL) °C	279 ± 2	276 ± 2	- 3
Weight residual 800°C (wt%)	6.1 ± 0.6	5.0 ± 0.6	- 1.1

Table 14 Test results of the re-manufactured prototype sample S39-2 with respect to the original prototype S39.

Property/Sample	S39	S39-2	Difference
Density (g/cm³)	1.191 ± 0.008	1.192 ± 0.009	+ 0.001
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	3.4 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.4	0
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	1.7 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.2	+ 0.7
Max lat elong, 28d (%)	1.6 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	- 0.9
Flexural modulus (MPa)	3780 ± 315	2890 ± 105	- 890
Flexural strength (MPa)	30.8 ± 0.9	25.9 ± 0.6	- 4.9
Resilience (kJ/m²)	3.24 ± 0.42	3.51 ± 0.24	+ 0.27
T(2wt% WL) °C	277 ± 2	265 ± 2	- 12
T(5 wt% WL) °C	309 ± 1	297 ± 2	- 12
Weight residual 800°C (wt%)	19.4 ± 1.0	15.8 ± 1.4	- 3.6

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Table 15 Test results of the re-manufactured prototype sample S40-2 with respect to the original prototype S40.

Property/Sample	S40	S40-2	Difference
Density (g/cm ³)	1.209 ± 0.004	1.209 ± 0.008	0
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	2.4 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.3	- 0.3
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	1.0 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.3	+ 0.5
Max lat elong, 28d (%)	0.6 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.2	- 0.1
Flexural modulus (MPa)	3850 ± 60	2895 ± 220	- 955
Flexural strength (MPa)	31.8 ± 0.9	28.7 ± 0.7	- 3.1
Resilience (kJ/m ²)	2.73 ± 0.25	2.91 ± 0.37	+ 0.18
T(2wt% WL) °C	278 ± 2	276 ± 3	- 2
T(5 wt% WL) °C	312 ± 3	308 ± 1	- 4
Weight residual 800°C (wt%)	23.3 ± 1.0	20.5 ± 1.4	- 2.8

Table 16 Test results of the re-manufactured prototype samples S43-2 and S43-3 with respect to the original prototype S43.

Property/Sample	S43	S43-2	S43-3	Diff43-2	Diff43-3
Density (g/cm ³)	1.152 ± 0.012	1.165 ± 0.002	1.165 ± 0.002	+ 0.013	+ 0.013
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	2.4 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.1	- 0.3	- 0.7
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	0.8 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	- 0.6	- 0.4

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Max lat elong, 28d (%)	0.5 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	- 0.2	- 0.1
Flexural modulus (MPa)	3835 ± 80	3370 ± 55	2905 ± 50	- 465	- 930
Flexural strength (MPa)	34.2 ± 1.4	32.2 ± 0.7	28.7 ± 0.2	- 2.0	- 5.5
Resilience (kJ/m²)	3.19 ± 0.17	3.06 ± 0.29	2.81 ± 0.34	- 0.13	- 0.38
T(2wt% WL) °C	277 ± 2	278 ± 1	276 ± 2	+ 1	- 1
T(5 wt% WL) °C	307 ± 2	307 ± 1	306 ± 2	0	- 1
Weight residual 800°C (wt%)	19.1 ± 0.6	20.2 ± 1.1	19.9 ± 0.4	+ 1.1	+ 0.8

Table 17 Test results of the re-manufactured prototype samples S44-2 and S44-3 with respect to the original prototype S44.

Property/Sample	S44	S44-2	S44-3	Diff44-2	Diff44-3
Density (g/cm³)	1.218 ± 0.001	1.236 ± 0.007	1.238 ± 0.001	+ 0.018	+ 0.020
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	6.5 ± 0.5	3.7 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.4	-2.8	-3.7
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	2.0 ± 0.3	0.8 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.1	-1.2	-0.9
Max lat elong, 28d (%)	1.4 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.2	-0.6	-0.8
Flexural modulus (MPa)	5465 ± 180	5250 ± 350	5005 ± 80	- 245	- 460
Flexural strength (MPa)	32.1 ± 0.7	30.3 ± 1.9	26.6 ± 0.6	- 1.8	- 5.5

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Resilience (kJ/m²)	3.84 ± 0.20	2.53 ± 0.12	2.11 ± 0.05	- 1.31	- 1.73
T(2wt% WL) °C	264 ± 2	272 ± 2	271 ± 1	+ 8	- 7
T(5 wt% WL) °C	295 ± 1	301 ± 2	300 ± 2	+ 6	- 5
Weight residual 800°C (wt%)	16.4 ± 0.4	18.2 ± 1.2	17.0 ± 0.8	+ 1.8	+ 0.6

The results reported on the re-manufacturing of CONENOR profiles based on virgin or recycled HDPE and PP are very interesting.

The re-manufacturing of the prototypes generally induces a progressive decrease of the mechanical properties. Indeed, for the prototypes based on HDPE (S39, S40, S44), and for the prototype based on PP (S43), either the flexural modulus, either the flexural strength of the composites monotonically decrease with the number of re-manufacturing cycles. Nevertheless, this decrease of the mechanical properties is not dramatic. As shown in Figure 37 and 38, the percent decrease of the flexural strength of prototypes as a function of the number of re-manufacturing cycles

8, for all the prototypes after 2 re-manufacturing processes, the decrease of the flexural modulus is always lower than 30% and the decrease of the flexural strength is lower than 20%.

Figure 37 Percent decrease of the flexural modulus of prototypes as a function of the number of re-manufacturing cycles

Figure 38 Percent decrease of the flexural strength of prototypes as a function of the number of re-manufacturing cycles

A different behaviour has been recorded only for the prototype S37, for which an increase of both the flexural modulus and flexural strength occur after re-manufacturing (see results for prototype S37-2 in Fig 39). Nevertheless, this sample is peculiar, being constituted by HDPE highly filled with wooded particles from furniture waste (wood content 62 wt%). With most probability, the problem for this specimen relies in the un-effective wetting of the filler during the production of the original prototypes S37. Indeed, as shown in 39, the size of the wooden particles in S37 are quite high (in the range of a few mm) and the adhesion of the filler with the matrix is low (see 39). Through the re-manufacturing, the wetting of the filler is improved, as well as its dispersion in the polymer matrix, and the final effect is the improvement of the mechanical properties of S37-2 with respect to S37. This explanation can be confirmed by the evidence that in the re-manufactured prototypes S37-2 an increase of the density and a decrease of the water absorption and thickness swelling are also recorded, confirming that the re-processing of the prototype contribute to an overall increase of the composite properties.

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Figure 39 SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces of the prototype S37: a) magnification 70 x; b) magnification 600x.

Overall the results do not indicate a clear limit for how many re-manufacturing loops the material may take. Obviously the final application acceptance criteria, which ever it might be, may limit if the product can be used in its intended use or maybe in another “fit-for-purpose” with other lower criteria.

A set of requested test samples by the University of Warwick of the components becoming used in the UK shelters was manufactured using re-manufactured Ecobulk composite materials. Unfortunately before they became delivered, the Covid-19 crisis caused the university becoming closed and the samples are yet waiting at Conenor for shipment permit from the University of Warwick.

Figure 40 Multilayer Ecobulk components with re-manufactured material in core layer, waiting for delivery to Warwick/UK after Covid-19

Once operations at the University of Warwick resumed, the components were successfully delivered. HDPE-based samples were characterised through 3-point-bending testing, Charpy testing, and normal and shear screw withdrawal force measurements. The material shipped to the UK (HDPE-based components) are also being used in Finland at KymiRing. The composition of this material is summarised on Table 18 and Table 19

Table 18 Product Outer Surface Layer

<u>PRODUCT OUTER SURFACE LAYER</u>	<u>%- w.</u>
GFRP-waste shavings from product manufacturing	35
recycled wood fibres (nordic pine)	14
talc	10
virgin HDPE (nat.)	20
recycled HDPE (mixed colors)	14
polymeric additives	6
color pigments	1
<u>TOTAL</u>	<u>100</u>

Table 19 Product Inner Core Layer

PRODUCT INNER CORE LAYER	%-W.
GFRP-waste from EoL wind blades	35
recycled wood fibres (nordic pine)	18
talc	10
recycled HDPE (mixed colors)	30
polymeric additives	7
<u>TOTAL</u>	<u>100</u>

The flexural properties were evaluated using a 250 kN Static Instron machine. As per ISO Standard 178 – 2010, Figure 41, a strain rate of 10 mm/min was applied. Specimens of hollow square beams, with a total length, support span distance, width and wall thickness of 1 m, 0.8 m, 125 mm and 10 mm, respectively. The flexural module and ultimate flexural strength were estimated from the force and displacement measurements. Support pins of Ø50 mm and a load pin of Ø100 mm were used. Ten (n = 10) samples were characterized and average values and standard deviations were determined.

Figure 41 3-point-bending set up

It was found that the flexural modulus and flexural strength of the material were 1045 MPa ± 243 MPa and 11.15 MPa ± 1.25 MPa, respectively. Figure 42 shows representative failure profiles of the specimens under 3-point-bending. Moreover, some specimens, as shown in Figure 43, presented manufacturing defects that may have initiated the failure of the material. Given that the presence

and location of these defects is difficult to predict, design service factors for structures shall consider the existence of these defects.

Figure 42 Representative failure profile under 3-point-bending

Figure 43 Defects on failure profile

Charpy tests were performed following ISO 179-1 -2010. Specimens type 1, with width, thickness and span length of 10 mm, 4 mm, and 62 mm. The specimens were tested in edge wise normal position and a 2 Joule impact hammer was used. The fracture strength was found to be $4.35 \text{ J/m}^2 \pm 1 \text{ J/m}^2$.

Sections of HDPE-GRP hollow beams (125 mm x 125 mm x 10 mm) were cut from the material received from Conenor. In these sections, five (5) different screw types were tested. M3, M4, and

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M5 wood screws (Figure 44), and No. 8 (Ø4 mm) and No. 10 (Ø5 mm) self-drilling screws (Figure 45). All screws were purchased from RS Components UK.

Figure 44 Pozidriv Countersunk Stainless Steel Wood Screw, A2 304, 5mm Thread, 25mm Length

Figure 45 RS PRO Bright Zinc Plated Steel Self-Drilling Screw No. 10 (Ø5 mm) x 25mm Long

The screws were placed in two symmetrical rows along the beam samples, leaving a margin of 50 mm from the ends, and with no less than 40 mm between each screw (Figure 46).

Figure 46 HDPE-GRP sections with screw specimens

As recommended by Conenor, pre-holes with 2.2 mm in diameter were done on the GRP sections to insert the wood screws. This was done using a pillar drill to guarantee that the screws are inserted perpendicular to the GRP beam surface. A drill driver was used to complete the screw insertion. The self-drilling screws were placed directly in the GRP section using a drill driver and a custom-made jig to drive the screws perpendicular to the surface. A total of 10 screws per type were tested.

The force of withdrawal was measured in a 100 kN Static Instron machine. The screws were withdrawn at a rate of 1 mm/min while the GRP sections were held in place with custom made fixing

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set up (Figure 47). During this process, the force of withdrawal was measured with a 10 kN force gauge. The maximum load that the screw supported before pulling out was then recorded.

Figure 47 Screw withdrawal force setup - Normal force

The results from the withdrawal force are listed in Table 20. The screw withdrawal force for the wood screws increased with the increase in screw diameter. This is likely to be caused by an increase of surface area and a higher volume of interaction between the material and the screws, leading to a larger volume of pull out material around the screws. This effect is illustrated in Figure 48.

Table 20 Screw withdrawal force for screw types and diameter considered

	Self-drilling screws		Wood screws		
	No. 8 (Ø4 mm)	No. 10 (Ø5 mm)	M3	M4	M5
Max force (n = 10) [N]	1080 ± 66	1053 ± 79	987 ± 93	1279 ± 57	1375 ± 113
95% Confidence interval (min – max) [N]	1039 – 1121	1005 – 1102	929 – 1045	1244 – 1315	1305 – 1444

Figure 48 Material pull out after M3 and M5 wood screw withdrawal

In the case of the self-drilling screws tested in this study, the diameter did not have an effect on the withdrawal force. The maximum force and the material pull out was lower in this type of screw than those of wood screws. This may be due to a lower thread height of the self-drilling screws. Figure 49 shows the material pull out after the withdrawal of a No. 10 (Ø5 mm).

Figure 49 Material pull out after No. 10 (Ø 5 mm) self-drilling screw withdrawal

In conclusion, these results suggest that a larger thread height, as it is the case of wood screws, played a more significant role in increasing the withdrawal force than an increase in diameter did.

Given that wood screws presented a higher withdrawal force than self-drilling screws, the use of these screws would be advised when higher forces are expected in a joint system. Moreover, self-drilling screws may be used in cases where lower forces are expected and it would be more practical to use those than to make pre-holes for the adequate insertion of wood screws.

The maximum withdrawal force under pure shear was measured (Figure 50). A maximum force of 1500 N was applied on the screws. While the screws were slightly bended under this force, no failure was achieved under these conditions. Therefore, screws are expected to fail under normal force conditions before they do under shear.

Figure 50 Screw withdrawal force setup - Shear force

5.4 TECNARO

All the samples were characterized at CNR through the following tests:

- Density (ASTM D792-13A)
- Flexural tests: Flexural modulus and flexural strength were calculated using the procedures described in ISO 178:2010;
- Water adsorption tests: these tests were performed using an internal CNR procedure. Small specimens (size > 2 cm x 2 cm x original thickness) were obtained by cutting the original panels. The specimens were conditioned at 25 °C and 50% relative humidity (RH) for at least 7 days. The weight of each specimen was measured with an analytical balance (± 0.0001 g). The thickness of the specimens was measured with a digital micrometer. The specimens were therefore immersed in distilled water and kept at 25 °C in the dark for 28 days. Therefore, the specimens were removed from water, the excess of water on their surface was gently removed with a filter paper and the specimens were weighted and measured again. The water absorption after 28 days of immersion (wt%) and the max thickness swelling (%) were calculated. For each sample, at least 5 specimens were tested. Average values and standard deviation values were calculated.

Test results on compounds ECO_1.1, ECO_1.9 and ECO_1.10 are reported elsewhere.

Table 21 Test results of the re-manufactured compounds ECO_1.1-2 and ECO_1.1-3 with respect to the original compound ECO 1.1.

Property/Sample	ECO_1.1	ECO_1.1-2	ECO_1.1-3
Density (g/cm ³)	1.02 ± 0.03	1.01 ± 0.02	1.02 ± 0.02
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	1.6 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.1
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	2.4 ± 0.3	2.3 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.2
Flexural modulus (MPa)	2740 ± 70	2555 ± 40	2320 ± 60
Flexural strength (MPa)	58.2 ± 0.4	53.7 ± 0.7	51.4 ± 0.3

Table 22 Test results of the re-manufactured compounds ECO_1.9-2 and ECO_1.9-3 with respect to the original compound ECO 1.9.

Property/Sample	ECO_1.9	ECO_1.9-2	ECO_1.9-3

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Density (g/cm³)	0.996 ± 0.008	0.998 ± 0.012	0.996 ± 0.006
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	2.1 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.4
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	1.5 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.1
Flexural modulus (MPa)	2435 ± 40	2280 ± 60	2175 ± 70
Flexural strength (MPa)	52.1 ± 0.9	49.6 ± 0.9	48.4 ± 1.3

Table 23 Test results of the re-manufactured compounds ECO_1.10-2 and ECO_1.10-3 with respect to the original compound ECO 1.10

Property/Sample	ECO_1.10	ECO_1.10-2	ECO_1.10-3
Density (g/cm³)	0.998 ± 0.009	0.996 ± 0.015	0.999 ± 0.007
Water adsorption, 28d (%)	2.3 ± 0.3	2.1 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.2
Max thickness swell, 28d (%)	1.4 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.1
Flexural modulus (MPa)	2680 ± 70	2550 ± 60	2435 ± 30
Flexural strength (MPa)	57.2 ± 1.2	54.8 ± 0.9	52.9 ± 1.0

The results reported on the re-manufacturing of TECNARO compounds: ECO1.1, ECO1.9 and ECO1.10 are very interesting.

The re-manufacturing of the prototypes induces a progressive decrease of the mechanical properties. Nevertheless, as shown in the following Figures 41-42, this worsening is not very high. In particular, for all the compounds after 2 re-manufacturing cycles, the decreases of the flexural modulus and strength are always lower than 20%.

More in details, the addition of a natural anti-oxidizing agent to ECO1.10 is effective on the retention of the properties during re-manufacturing, as the behaviour of the compound ECO_1.10, containing a natural anti-oxidizing agent, is comparable or even better with respect to the behaviour of the compound ECO 1.9, realized through the use of a traditional and commercial available anti-oxidizing agent.

Figure 51 Percent decrease of the flexural modulus of Tecnar compounds as a function of the number of re-manufacturing cycles

Figure 52 Percent decrease of the flexural strength of Tecnar compounds as a function of the number of re-manufacturing cycles

6 Conclusion

Good progress has been made in determining the re-manufacturing possibilities of a wide variety of polymers and reinforcements through a number of manufactured samples. It should be noted that much of the work in the latter part of the period was affected by the pandemic and therefore there is more work to be completed within the project, as noted by the partners. Samples are waiting at various partners' facilities and at external users facilities.

The report illustrates that if components can be split back to parts of a single material basic material (or material family) then good quality components can be manufactured with only moderate loss of properties. It is not true that only down-cycling can be achieved.

Indeed, in some case the recovery process can actually improve performance, admittedly because the initial mixing or 'wetting out' of the reinforcement was less than perfect in the initial product. This is also evidenced by an increase in density and reduced moisture absorption.

Partners report that the materials were generally good to use, with minor problems encountered in feeding the materials because of their geometry, a problem that can relatively easily overcome.

The partners also report that the disassembly of automotive components was successful as a manual operation. Whether this is economical is another question being addressed elsewhere in EcoBulk. (D4.5 in M45).

Overall the results have not yet defined the limit of loops of recycling but clearly that will happen. This is affected strongly by the materials used and the products made. Conenor have demonstrated that using their process a wide variety of waste products can be combined as the bulk of construction products, which in turn can still be recycled and remanufactured so the 'loops' can be as high as 5 or 6 at the moment.

Further test results will be reported in D4.5 towards the end of the project.

Update 18.12.20 – This report has been reviewed in order to see whether extra results, delayed by COVID, can be included. No extra results are available and therefore will be updated in '*D4.5: Demonstration results of the automotive composite parts*' and '*D4.6: Demonstration results of the furniture and building products*'